

Key Facts

Duration: September 2024 – August 2027

EU Contribution: € 8.443.840,80

Programme: Digital Europe Programme

The Consortium

Coordinator: Information Technology for Market Leadership (ITML)

Partners: The consortium includes 14 stakeholders from industrial end users, technological partners and SMEs with diverse and complementary capabilities and thus delivers ample capacity to carry out the presented project.

The Challenge

The European Union's Cyber Resilience Act (CRA) introduces stringent new cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements throughout their entire lifecycle. For many manufacturers, distributors, and especially SMEs, navigating this new regulatory landscape is complex and resource-intensive.

CRACoWi's primary objective is to **simplify and automate CRA compliance**. The project is developing an **innovative digital "wizard" to help businesses** meet these new standards efficiently, from a product's inception to its end-of-life.

The Mission

The project's mission is to empower businesses, particularly SMEs, to build security into their products by design and maintain it post-market. To achieve this, CRACoWi is building an AI-powered tool that provides:

- Automatic CRA self-assessment: guiding companies through the compliance requirements.
- Automated documentation generation: streamlining the paperwork needed for certification.
- Support for cybersecurity certification: helping products meet official EU standards.
- Continuous vulnerability monitoring: emphasising proactive security management across the entire product lifecycle.

The Impact

Impact on businesses (especially SMEs)

- Reduced compliance burden: simplifying and de-risking the process of adhering to the CRA, making it accessible for smaller companies with limited resources.
- Enhanced product security: embedding cybersecurity from the start, resulting in more secure digital products for the European market.
- Enhanced product security: embedding cybersecurity from the start, resulting in more secure digital products for the European market.

Contribution to EU Policy

- Streamlined CRA implementation: providing a concrete, scalable tool to support the effective rollout of the Cyber Resilience Act across member states.
- Strengthened digital economy: contributing directly to the EU's goal of a more secure, resilient, and trustworthy digital economy by elevating cybersecurity practices throughout the supply chain.

Knowledge and capacity building

- Widespread dissemination & awareness: the project ensures all stakeholders, from SMEs to regulatory bodies, are informed and empowered to navigate the CRA.
- Enhanced cooperation: fostering collaboration between industry, regulatory authorities, and cybersecurity experts to build a unified European front against cyber threats.
- CRAcademy: delivering clear and practical information about the CRA through FAQs, blogs, expert insights, workshops, webinars, and more. It serves as a one-stop shop for staying informed and strengthening organisational cybersecurity resilience.